
FEATURES OF DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract.

Currently, the demand for distance learning is steadily growing. This is explained by the fact that it is flexible, convenient and accessible, it implies wide variability and differentiation in the choice of both content and forms of education. This article discusses the features of distance learning technologies in higher education.

Keywords.

distance learning, interactive interaction, student-centered learning, communication technologies.

Introduction:

The present stage of development of distance learning methods can be called a period of accumulation of experience. Teams of teachers, creating distance courses for different areas, gain experience in conducting classes, find the most effective forms of education. Pedagogical findings obtained in various educational areas can be useful to many practitioners when building their own distance learning methods.

Speaking further about the merits and advantages of distance learning, first, it is necessary to keep in mind the prospects for introducing this form into the system of advanced training for teachers. These prospects also have quite specific economic prerequisites. Simple calculations show that the costs of conducting traditional face-to-face courses (including the costs of maintaining buildings, classrooms, computer classes) are higher than the costs of organizing distance courses (if students already have computers with Internet access in schools). The work of teachers takes place in the university computer class, and this increases the return on the technology installed in the university. Some students have the opportunity to work on a home computer, and thus the students actually pay for

the utility costs of training from their home budget (in exchange for the amenities they receive)¹⁹³.

Thus, distance learning is the most democratic form of education that allows the public to receive education, regardless of where they live. Distance learning is a set of technologies that ensure the delivery of the bulk of the studied material to students, the interactive interaction of students and teachers in the learning process, providing students with the opportunity to work independently to master the material being studied, as well as in the learning process.

Modern distance learning is based on the use of the following main elements:

- Information transmission media (mail, television, radio, information communication networks);

- Methods dependent on the technical environment for information exchange.

Distance learning methods are used in higher education, the system of professional development for teachers, and in the system of training managerial personnel.

Main part:

The specifics of distance learning leaves its mark on the technologies used. This is due to the role of the teacher in the educational process. If earlier in the traditional education system the teacher occupied the central place as an interpreter of knowledge, now, in the conditions of informatization, this place increasingly belongs to the student, who independently acquires knowledge from various sources. Under these conditions, the teacher acts as a coordinator, helping the student to acquire knowledge and apply it in practice. The concern of the teacher is the choice of methods and technologies for the implementation of their activities. Moreover, the main role here is played by the methods of active and developing learning.

The next feature of distance learning is the possibility of implementing student-centered learning, i.e. learning that takes into account the personal qualities of the student, his capabilities and educational goals. Technologies for the implementation of independent work of a student based on interactive multimedia teaching aids make it possible to build individualized differentiated learning¹⁹⁴.

¹⁹³ Лугин В.Г. Формы и методы Дистанционного обучения. Режим доступа <http://repetitmaster.ru/forms-and-methods-remote-education.html>

¹⁹⁴ Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna, Nurullayev Bahrom Komiljonovich Information-communication technologies and multimedia in foreign language classes // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №6 (47). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/information-communication-technologies-and-multimedia-in-foreign-language-classes>

Thus, distance-learning technologies are pedagogical technologies based on the widespread use of developing teaching methods, problematic and research methods, combined with the maximum use of achievements in the field of information and communication technologies.

Based on the definition of distance learning as an organization of cognitive activity based on self-education, in which direct pedagogical communication is minimized, it is necessary to determine the didactic principles that distinguish distance learning and underlie the construction of a didactic model.

So, in distance learning, the following principles should be observed.

1. The learning process is built mainly on the independent cognitive activity of the student.
2. The student's cognitive activity must be active.
3. Distance learning must be student-centered.

Increasing the efficiency of the educational process is possible only based on the individualization of educational and cognitive activity. Such personalized learning in conditions of mass demand is possible only based on high learning technologies built on computer tools and technologies.

Pedagogical technologies belong to the category of social technologies aimed at personal development. At the same time, a person undergoing changes acts as the initial and final result of social technology. One of the most important distinguishing features of social technologies is the necessity and inevitability of feedback, which allows you to control the process of influencing a person with the help of certain technologies and adjust the technologies themselves. This becomes especially important in distance learning, when there is a change in didactic methods and means by which educational tasks are solved, not only the nature of the organization of the educational process changes, but also the forms of educational and pedagogical activity [21,14]. The strengthening of the role of independent work of students, the indirectness of pedagogical communication lead to the complication of pedagogical technologies and their change. At the same time, pedagogical technologies of distance learning mean technologies of pedagogical communication, ways of organizing the cognitive activity of students, as well as ways of organizing knowledge quality control.

Pedagogical technologies of distance learning are pedagogical technologies of indirect and direct communication using electronic telecommunications and didactic tools. At the same time, didactic means of distance learning are understood as materials, methods and techniques of teaching, forms of organization of

educational and cognitive activities, taking into account the limitations of direct communication with the teacher.

A feature of pedagogical technologies is the outstripping nature of their development in relation to technical means. The fact is that the introduction of a computer in education leads to a revision of all components of the educational process. In the interactive environment "student - computer - teacher" more attention should be paid to the activation of imaginative thinking through the use of technologies that activate the right hemisphere, synthetic thinking. Moreover, this means that the presentation of educational material should reproduce the thought of the teacher in the form of images. In other words, the main point in the pedagogical technologies of distance learning is the visualization of thoughts, information, knowledge, the creation of new ways of pedagogical communication, the correction of traditional forms of organization of educational activities¹⁹⁵.

The educational process in distance learning includes all the main forms of the traditional organization of the educational process, which allow in practice a flexible combination of independent cognitive activity of students with various sources of information, operational and systematic interaction with the lead teacher of the course or tutor and group work of students.

Information technologies used in distance education can be divided into three groups:

- Technologies for presenting educational information;
- Technologies for the transfer of educational information;
- Technologies of storage and processing of educational information.

Together, they form distance-learning technologies. At the same time, when implementing educational programs, technologies for the transfer of educational information are of particular importance, which, in essence, provide the learning process and its support.

The main role played by telecommunication technologies in distance learning is to provide educational dialogue. Learning without feedback, without constant dialogue between the teacher and the student is impossible. Learning (as opposed to self-education) is a dialogical process by definition. In full-time education, the possibility of dialogue is determined by the very form of organization of the educational process, the presence of a teacher and a student in one place at one

¹⁹⁵ Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS // ORIENSS. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/innovative-methods-of-teaching-in-educational-institution>

time. With distance learning, the educational dialogue must be organized using telecommunication technologies [10,288].

Communication technologies can be divided into two types: on-line and off-line. The former provide real-time information exchange, that is, a message sent by the sender, upon reaching the recipient's computer, is immediately sent to the appropriate output device. When using off-line technologies, received messages are stored on the recipient's computer. The user can view them with the help of special programs at a convenient time for him. Unlike face-to-face learning, where the dialogue is conducted in real time (on-line), in distance learning it can also go in the mode with a delayed response (off-line).

The main advantage of off-line technologies is that they are less demanding on computer resources and communication line bandwidth. They can be used even when connected to the Internet via dial-up lines (in the absence of a permanent connection to the Internet).

Technologies of this kind include e-mail, mailing lists, and teleconferencing. With the help of the list-server, distribution of educational information can be organized, personal communication between the teacher and the student is established with the help of e-mail, and the teleconference allows organizing a collective discussion of any issue. All these technologies allow you to exchange messages between different computers connected to the Internet [2, 83].

The development of information technologies and means of telecommunications creates the basis for the implementation of educational programs at a qualitatively new level. The creation of high-speed telecommunications and the development of real-time technologies makes it possible to implement models of a distributed educational environment built on technologies for remote access to information resources and computer communication tools.

Despite the lack of telecommunications resources, these technologies are already firmly established in the practice of educational institutions. Unique laboratory experimental and computing complexes have become available thanks to automation tools and computer technologies for remote control and form the basis of scientific service on the Internet.

Conclusion:

The advantages of real-time technologies are obvious. They allow combining the material and computing resources of educational and scientific centers to solve complex problems, attract leading experts and create distributed scientific laboratories, organize online access to shared resources and joint computational

and laboratory experiments, and implement joint scientific projects and educational programs.

All of the above shows that information and communication technologies can be widely used in the field of distance education both for the presentation and delivery of educational materials, and for accompanying the educational process, providing an educational dialogue.

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